

Paper 29**LEARNING AND CAPABILITY ACQUISITION:
A CASE STUDY OF THE INDIAN AUTOMOBILE
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Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore – 575 001.**Abstract**

This study analyzes the impact of government policy regime on the learning and capability acquisition of firms over time. Through a case study analysis of the Indian automotive industry, the study develops three hypotheses relating policy regimes with learning strategies of firms.

The study tests these hypotheses through a model of learning using a panel data for the Indian automotive industry. It finds that speed of knowledge assimilation is more important in the liberalized policy regime vis-à-vis protection when knowledge assimilation per se was a more Important economic goal.

The Indian auto industry became the 4th largest in the world with sales increasing 9.5 per cent year-on-year to 4.02 million units (excluding two wheelers) in 2017. It was the 7th largest manufacturer of commercial vehicles in 2017.

The Two Wheelers segment dominates the market in terms of volume owing to a growing middle class and a young population. Moreover, the growing interest of the companies in exploring the rural markets further aided the growth of the sector.

Keywords: Growth, Learning, Capabilities, Industrial Policy, Automobile industry, Asia, India.**1. INTRODUCTION**

It is well recognized in industrial organization theory and empirical literature that learning as a capability is a major factor in explaining interfirm performance differences. The success of newly industrialized countries (NICs), for example, has shown that technological progress is not merely guided by changes in relative prices, nor does competitiveness depend upon relative factor endowments. It is more than acquiring the technological blue prints and involves a learning process. This is more so in the context of late comers to industrialization, where governments have actively pursued industrial regulation and protection to allow firms to grow and learn to compete. Therefore, it is an interesting research question to ask: how does regulation impact firm

learning and growth? This paper analyzes the role played by government policies in transforming the learning abilities of the firms and the markets with reference to the Indian automobile industry.

Based on a case study analysis of automotive firms in the Indian Industry, three hypotheses are developed relating firm learning with policy regime. These hypotheses are then empirically tested using a panel data of 13 firms across a 38 year period, an interval subdivided into three different industrial policy regimes eras: protection, deregulation and liberalization.

2. INDUSTRIAL POLICY REGIMES IN INDIA AND IMPACT ON FIRM LEARNING

[1][2][3][4]

Protection: 1970-84 —Macro Economic Environment

During the protection phase, the industry's output was controlled by licensing production capacity and restricting output to single models so as to minimize the foreign exchange outflows due to the imports of components. Industrial policy did not allow capital imports or foreign direct investment (FDI). Further, complicated rules on imports made access to technology difficult and slowed down the learning process of firms.

Market Structure and Technology

The market structure was concentrated with entry barriers and restrictions to creating capacities and adding new product lines. While General Motors and Ford shut down their operations in India, business groups like the Birla and the Walchand group entered the industry. In 1960, there were three manufacturers, initially producing with licensed technology from US, UK and Italy; Premier Automobiles limited, Hindustan Motors and Standard Motors private limited, each producing very small outputs and Mahindra manufacturing jeeps. Product specific licensing policy forced companies to enter niche segments where each enjoyed a monopoly. The market structure was thus concentrated and the firms relied on licensed technology and foreign equity participation as the means to growth. In mid seventies, the commercial vehicle industry was allowed unlimited production capacity and an automatic capacity expansion of 25% every five years.

External Institutions

Supplier capabilities in India were not well developed, and TML had various training programs to develop its capabilities. Auto component manufacturing was reserved for small-scale industry but lack of volumes did not allow consolidation in the industry through a hierarchical organization of capabilities (also known as tierization) in the supplier industry. It remained highly fragmented and technologically underdeveloped during this phase.

Impact on Learning

In the presence of regulations on product lines and capacity expansions, the only means to growth was access to foreign equity which would give them superior technology. According to Narayana's study (1997), in the protection regime, in the absence of major acquisitions or diversifications, firms with foreign equity grew faster than others because of the resource advantage they possessed. Thus, in the protection phase, the firm growth was dependent on its

absorptive capacity that enables them to learn and internalize their foreign partner's technological knowledge.

Deregulation: 1984-91

Macro Environment

The industrial policy statements of 1977 and 1980 marked the beginning of deregulation by relaxing the regulations governing production licenses, foreign collaboration, asset size and the scope of industrial operations. In 1985, policy of broad banding was introduced with allowed manufacturers to make use of economies of scale and scope by manufacturing several product lines. Further, the technology imports were allowed and firms resorted to imports as a means to growth. Government entered into partnership with Suzuki in 1982 and in 1984, which led to the setting up of Maruti Udyog Limited (Maruti). The macro economic situation deteriorated in the mid 80s because of liberalized imports, rupee appreciation and drain on foreign exchange reserves. The government was forced to devalue the currency in 1991 and resort to IMF for liberalization program. Between 1984 and 1987, the Yen appreciated 200 times which hurt the Japanese joint ventures adversely.

Market Structure

Maruti manufactured 12000 vehicles challenging the market shares of the existing manufacturers and eventually becoming the market leader by 1991. Entry in the Passenger car segment was still restricted, with three players until early 1991—Maruti, Hindustan motors and Premier automobiles limited (PAL) with market shares of 60%, 13% and 23%. Standard Motors exited from the industry in the late 1980s. Thus, from this phase, the market structure changed in favor of the government joint venture-Maruti Udyog Limited and the output of automobile industry increased by nearly 400%. The commercial vehicle segment was liberalized and saw the entry of Japanese joint ventures like DCM-Toyota, Eicher-Mitsubishi Swaraj-Mazda and Allwyn-Nissan. However, most of them suffered set backs due to macro economic environment and foreign exchange appreciation.

External Institutions

The entry of Maruti also changed the supplier relations within the industry with the help of government sponsored training programs and cluster building. The presence of Japanese joint ventures in the same region created economies of industrial agglomeration. This also resulted in a widespread use of Japanese work practices that relied on cooperative agreements between suppliers and OEMs.

Impact on Learning

During the deregulation period, firms relied on technology imports and growth through spillovers from new competitors. Allowing firms to invest in several product lines resulted in firm learning as firms like Tata Motors introduced special purpose vehicles and platforms for moving towards passenger car segment. The institutional support for developing supplier capabilities led to flexible supplier relationships whereby, firms could adjust demand downwards through detailed cost negotiations. For instance, Maruti was also able to expand its capacity in

press shop from 130,000 to 180,000 without any significant capital outlays by having flexible labor practices and joint ventures

Liberalization: 1992-2008: Macro Environment

In 1993, the passenger car industry was completely delicensed followed by an entry of multinationals in this segment. This also encouraged existing firms to form joint ventures with foreign firms. From August 1991 to April 2002, the auto industry garnered 5.48% of the total foreign direct investment approved during this period (Government of India, Ministry of Commerce and Industry 2002).

Market Structure

The liberalized policies allowed firms to take advantage of low cost sourcing across the globe which in turn gave rise to modular relationships between suppliers and OEMs. For example, Sona Koyo has set up an engineering design and outsourcing company for its international clients. Rico Auto and Sundaram fasteners have laboratories with latest softwares for reverse engineering, designing and testing of parts. Such capabilities enable these firms to take up turnkey projects with low switching costs for the OEMs. At the same time, some firms did not acquire the capabilities to sustain competitiveness in the liberalized policy environment. For example, two firms exited the industry in the nineties: DCM Toyota and PAL. Both firms were taken over by multinationals, Daewoo in case of DCM and Fiat in the case of PAL. PAL exited from the industry after a failed partnership with Peugeot of France, and was taken over by Fiat.

External Institutions

With severe infrastructural and supply bottlenecks, resulting partly from past government policy of neglecting infrastructure and reserving components for the officially defined small scale industries, manufacturers were compelled to encourage partnerships among their suppliers to reduce mutual vulnerability. Supplier associations were introduced by Japanese manufacturers to enable diffusion of best practices. The Automotive component manufacturers association was an industrial lobby actively engaged in pursuing the suppliers' interests in the organized industry.

Impact on Learning

The liberalized environment exposed firms to new competition and encouraged them to undertake research and development activities, which increased during this time period. Firms introduced variety of models and the time span between new launches was also declining rapidly, indicating that firms were actively involved in new product development. For example, at Tata Motors, a new technology group was set up at engineering research center for simultaneous engineering and joint product development with suppliers. Thus, during liberalization, firms resorted to learning through innovation and spillovers resulting from inter-firm relations. Changing inter-firm relations involved setting up a new organizational form in 1995 to promote technology acquisition in the component industry. The holding company structure gives Tata Motors the flexibility to partner with multiple global majors to access cutting edge technology and also facilitates the pooling of resources, capabilities and the creation of a common infrastructure and managerial expertise.

Similarly, in the year 2004, Maruti started a “Centre for Excellence”, a joint investment between Maruti and some of its tier-I suppliers, with the OEM holding the majority stake. The Centre promoted three kinds of activities through a cluster of five to six companies: productivity improvements such as TPM, Kaizen and training for Japanese production systems; quality improvement program, where a top-down approach is adopted and emphasis is on training principles of TQM and system audits.

Year	Tata Motor	Ashok Leyland	Hindustan Motors	Maruti Udyog Ltd	Mahindra	Premier Automobile	Bajaj Tempo	Hyundai Motor India Ltd
1990	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.2	0.2	1.6	0.6	
1991	0.6	1.1	0.4	0.4	0.2	1.3	2.2	
1992	1.1	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.2	2.0	2.1	
1993	2.6	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.4	1.2	2.1	
1994	2.7	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.8	0.0	1.9	
1995	1.4	0.9	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	1.7	
1996	1.7	0.1	0.4	0.2	1.2	3.5	1.5	
1997	2.0	0.6	0.6	0.2	0.7	0.3	1.3	
1998	1.6	0.5	0.7	0.4	0.9	0.1	1.6	0.05
1999	1.2	0.7	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.4	1.0	0.02
2000	1.1	0.9	0.3	0.5	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.00
2001	1.1	0.9	0.5	0.5	1.8	0.0	2.2	0.00
2002	1.3	1.0	0.6	0.2	1.7		2.3	0.10

Source: SIAM Facts and Figures (2004), Annual reports.

Table 1: R&D Intensity (R&D expenditure as % of Sales)

Firms like Tata Motors and Maruti entered into strategic partnerships and also evolved new forms of supplier relations to promote joint product development and learning through spillovers. For example, in the liberalized regime, Tata’s technology strategy focused on acquiring strategic partnerships and import of technological know-how. It imported technology for development of fuel injected gasoline engines from AVL, Austria in 1992, body styling from IDEA, Italy, process capability for welding from HLS, Germany and engine testing from Le Moteur Moderne, France. In 1994, the machine tool division built robots for the first time, with technology imported from Nachi-Fujikashi of Japan. Tata entered the passenger car segment in 1998 and in 2000, in an effort to focus on its core business of design and development of vehicles, it hived off the machine tool division into a separate company called Tata Automation Limited (TAL).

3. DATA SOURCE

This study is based on annual production data for a sample of 13 firms in the four-wheeler automobile industry, obtained from the Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers and Automobile Component Manufacturers Association, for thirty-eight years from 1970-2008 and the time period is divided into three industrial policy regimes: protection (1970-84); deregulation

(1985-91) and liberalization (1992-2008). The thirteen firms in the four-wheeler segment can be divided into three groups: Group one is those born in the protection period (pre-1970) and group two those born in the post-regulatory period (post-1985). A third group of firms is the multinational firms which entered after 1996. The data is unbalanced with exit and entry in the liberalized regime.

The descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) of the explanatory variables are presented in table 3. Table 4 shows the compound annual average growth rates (CAGR) in different policy regimes. Growth rates of the six firms in the protection phase were higher compared to the liberalization period. In the sample of six firms, only one firm-Tata Motors did better during the liberalization as compared to the protection period. In regime III, multinational firms had the highest growth rates. To summarize, regime I was driven by growth in the commercial vehicle segment, with firms like Ashok Leyland, Tata, Mahindra and Bajaj Tempo displaying above average industry growth rates. Regime II and III were driven by growth in the passenger car segment, with the entry of Maruti in 1985 and multinational players in mid 1990s. The overall industrial growth has been the highest in regime III, the main drivers of which are the multinational firms in the passenger car sector. One can estimate the model using either the random effects or fixed effects models. The former assumes that firm-specific factors are uncorrelated with size and age, whereas, the latter allows for such a correlation. The Hausman's statistics can help to choose the method of estimation. It tests the null hypothesis of no correlation (i.e., random effect model). The Hausman's statistic supports the null hypothesis of zero correlation between firm specific factors with size. Hence, the study uses a one-way Random Effects model to estimate the coefficients.

Firms/ policy regimes	Production (Units)	Growth (Log Differences)	Lagged Output (Log)	Lagged Output (Log)- Rival Firms	Lagged Growth-Rival Firms	Sample Size
Tata Motors-Regime 1	383921	0.143	11.377	12.339	0.116	13
Regime 2	272754	0.160	8.075	8.755	0.111	7
Regime 3	343366	0.113	11.240	12.237	0.115	17
Ashok Leyl-Regime 1	10831	0.085	9.144	11.526	0.042	13
Regime 2	19875	0.074	9.805	12.534	0.125	7
Regime 3	43356	0.047	10.546	13.629	0.102	17
Hind.motors-Regime 1	23173	-0.002	10.020	11.383	0.056	13
Regime 2	26158	-0.068	10.224	12.497	0.137	7
Regime 3	22004	-0.036	9.978	13.643	0.105	17
Mahindras-Regime 1	28019	0.073	10.075	11.372	0.036	13
Regime 2	58227	0.028	10.937	12.383	0.141	7
Regime 3	138516	0.072	11.726	13.514	0.105	17
Premier Auto-Regime 1	18811	0.040	9.771	11.440	0.049	13
Regime 2	35312	0.017	10.442	12.473	0.127	7
Regime 3	14032	52.035	51.341	13.656	0.108	8
BajajTempo-Regime 1	7276	0.109	8.695	11.561	0.041	13
Regime 2	15138	0.010	9.611	12.545	0.127	7
Regime 3	19860	0.004	9.788	13.650	0.103	17
Eicher -Regime 2	3745	28.473	34.060	12.590	0.121	6
Regime 3	12524	0.088	9.089	13.664	0.101	17
Swaraj -Regime 2	3093	14.186	21.031	12.589	0.121	7
Regime 3	6290	64.016	61.606	13.671	0.101	6
DCM-Regime 2	2502	14.272	20.769	12.591	0.121	7
Regime 3	6564	0.072	8.562	13.668	0.101	17
Maruti -Regime 2	98865	0.241	11.223	12.282	0.069	7
Regime 3	415556	0.109	12.717	13.184	0.097	17
Hyundai India -Regime 3	202363	35.713	47.692	13.599	0.090	11
Ford India-Regime 3	24258	47.188	57.084	13.667	0.100	9
Toyota Kirl.-Regime 3	36477	41.397	52.030	13.661	0.099	10
Industry-Regime 1	122617	0.057	-	-	-	13
Regime 2	326894	0.085	-	-	-	7
Regime 3	1101079	0.103	-	-	-	17

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Firms	Regime 1-1970-84			Regime 2-1985-91			Regime 3-1992-2008		
	CAGR	Mean	CV	CAGR	Mean	CV	CAGR	Mean	CV
Tata Motors	6.06	5.71	2.82	11.83	11.83	0.67	11.28	11	0.57
Ashok Leyland	9.66	8.95	1.89	9.43	7.40	1.36	7.28	7	0.84
Hindmotors	0.81	4.88	7.01	-3.95	-5.33	-3.27	-6.03	-6	-0.63
MUL	0.00			56.57	16.70	1.20	10.02	11	0.28
Mahindra	7.45	10.32	2.22	5.11	3.50	3.00	5.41	7	0.46
PAL	1.98	8.38	4.39	5.16	2.82	5.96	-47.21	-81	-0.71
BT	10.78	11.16	1.53	1.49	1.12	15.00	1.61	6	1.30
Eicher				24.94	42.97	1.79	15.38	12	0.44
DCM				7.03	9.43	3.24	15.77	-10	-7.25
Swaraj				18.86	21.53	1.68	11.02	8	0.65
HMIL							31.19	33.25	0.37
TKMIL							22.22	28.48	0.75
FIL							0.21	20.00	0.71
GMIL							26.59	26.59	0.45
Industry	6.45%	7.42%	1.95	8.32%	7.51%	0.96	9.84%	11.50%	0.33

*Growth rate for PAL for Regime 3 is from 1992-2000 and for DCM it is from 1992-1999.

Table 4: Compound Average Growth Rate (%)

4. CONCLUSION

The economic success of emerging economies in the late seventies sparked off debates on several issues like the role of government versus the private sector, export oriented strategy versus import substituting industrialization and a combination of the two. In this context, this thesis undertakes a case study of the growth of the Indian automobile Industry across three policy regimes, focusing on learning and capability acquisition. The objective has been to study whether policy regime can influence firm level learning. If so, then it provides a justification to the infant industry argument from a developing country perspective as well as highlights the lessons to be learnt from successful learners. The study relies on a qualitative case study approach, complemented by quantitative techniques.

While the literature on technological capability acquisition is rich in documenting the empirical details of the process and sequence of capability acquisition, it suffers from subjective classification of capabilities and a static analysis of capabilities that are changing over time. The study has tried to integrate empirical case studies with the literature on learning by applying a dynamic model of learning to the Indian industry. The study examined the dynamic nature of learning process by looking at the time path of output across thirteen major automobile firms. The model is estimated for the Indian industry for a sample of thirteen four wheeler firms across three policy regimes, divided into twelve year, seven year and seventeen year period. The study uses random effects panel data estimation, with time trend and structural dummies as shift variables for the regime changes.

To conclude, the paper demonstrates that learning varies by the policy regime. Learning is also firm-specific, defined by the technology strategy and capabilities of the firms, which is not captured by the traditional industrial organization theory. The study rejects the hypothesis of independence between firm size and firm growth, known as Gibrat's law.

Results indicate that relation between firm size and growth differs by policy regime. The results indicate that during protection accumulation of stock of knowledge was more important, whereas during liberalization, the speed of knowledge accumulation was more important. From a policy perspective, while protection encourages acquisition of production capabilities of, it does not equip the firm with the learning capabilities necessary for survival in a competitive environment. This is shown by the fact that some of the firms that acquired learning also exited the industry in a liberalized policy regime, unable to face the competition. What is required is an ability to adapt to the changing market conditions. These conclusions also give pointers to further research to incorporate the impact of quality and coordination capabilities in the model of learning.

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